

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Artificial Intelligence for Decarbonisation's Virtual Centre of Excellence

Understanding Heat Pump
Performance: Improving
Efficiency and Adoption

**27 January 2025 -
7 February 2025**

Contents

1	Executive Summary	4
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Background	5
2.1.1	Heat pump performance	6
2.2	DSG objectives	7
3	Data overview	8
3.1	Dataset description	8
3.2	Data quality	9
3.3	Exploratory data analysis	10
3.3.1	Heat pump types	10
3.3.2	Geographical coverage	11
3.3.3	Factor analysis of installation data	12
4	Scientific approach	16
4.1	Time-series data analysis	16
4.2	Installation data analysis	18
4.3	Reinforcement learning-based adaptive control strategy	19
5	Time-series symptoms of underperformance	19
5.1	Sample selection	19
5.1.1	Geographical distribution	20
5.1.2	Outdoor & Indoor temperatures	20
5.1.3	Performance differences between high-temperature and low-temperature air-source heat pumps	21
5.1.4	LT ASHP household data	21
5.1.5	LT ASHP winter data availability and COP	23
5.1.6	Data preprocessing steps previously conducted by the Electrification of Heat team	24
5.2	Approach 1: Direct clustering of peaks and cycles	25
5.2.1	Empirical mode decomposition with K-means	25
5.2.2	Z-Score peak transformation with dynamic time warping K-means	28
5.3	Approach 2: Clustering of features extracted from time-series	33
5.3.1	Feature extraction	33

5.3.2	K-means clustering of the features	36
5.3.3	Relationship between weather compensation curve R^2 value and heat pump performance	40
5.4	Approach 3: Degradation of COP over time	41
6	Causal inference and analysis of performance based on installation data	43
6.1	Sample selection	43
6.2	Approach 1: Non-linear analysis on installation data	43
6.3	Approach 2: Causal analysis	46
6.4	Approach 3: Cross-sectional regression model	47
7	Discussion and limitations	51
8	Conclusion and future work	52
9	Team members	53
10	Principal investigator	55
	References	56
A	Geographical coverage	58
B	Winter data availability and COP	58
C	One-dimensional peak finding algorithm	63
D	Clusters between COP and different power consumption features extracted	63
E	Silhouette scores for DTW clustering	64
F	SHAP value impact on SPFH4 prediction	65
G	Reinforcement learning based adaptive control strategy	66
G.1	Research questions	67
G.1.1	Reinforcement Learning based adaptive control strategy	67
G.2	Sample selection	67
G.3	Approach	68

G.4	Experimental results	69
G.4.1	Predictive model evaluation	70
G.4.2	RL agent performance	70
G.5	Implications and future considerations	72
H	EMD applied to various time series	72
I	Flow temperature vs external temperature plot for property ID 3056	73

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ) through the AI for Decarbonisation’s Virtual Centre of Excellence (ADViCE) within the AI for Decarbonisation Innovation Programme.

1 Executive Summary

This report presents an analysis of automated methods for diagnosing underperformance in domestic heat pumps—a crucial step toward accelerating the transition to low-carbon heating solutions. The challenge owner, ADViCE, is a collaborative initiative among Digital Catapult, Energy Systems Catapult, and The Alan Turing Institute. This Data Study Group aimed to develop data-driven approaches to identify performance issues related to system configuration, installation quality, and control strategies. The ultimate objective is to reduce through-life costs and increase homeowner confidence in adopting energy-efficient heat pumps.

The study leverages the UK Electrification of Heat Trial dataset, which includes high-resolution (2-minute) monitoring data from 740 heat pump installations, along with extensive property characteristics, installation details, and demographic information. Data quality assessments confirmed that the dataset is appropriate and sufficiently detailed, despite the absence of labelled data for supervised methods.

A multifaceted methodology was employed.

- Time-series analyses extracted key operational features such as cycling frequency, peak patterns, and seasonal variations using techniques including Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) and a z-score based peak detection algorithm. Clustering approaches, notably K-means with dynamic time warping, were applied to differentiate high- and low-performing heat pumps based on these features.
- Installation data analyses to understand the relationship between performance and installation features. Approaches included non-linear regression with CatBoost and SHAP for feature interpretation, causal discovery algorithms and cross-sectional regression models to examine the influence of technical specifications, building characteristics, and installation quality on performance.

An exploratory study on reinforcement learning-based adaptive control further contributed insights into optimising operational performance.

Key findings:

- The Z-Score peak detection with SDTW K-means shows promise for

effectively extracting time-series patterns (silhouette scores: 0.477 for $k=2$, 0.421 for $k=5$), though further hyperparameter tuning is required.

- Feature-based clustering using power consumption and weather compensation data proved inconclusive.
- Non-linear and causal analyses of installation data revealed no strong associations with performance, while linear regression showed significant links with house type, commissioning quality, and especially floor area—suggesting that larger properties, likely better insulated, tend to exhibit improved performance.

Recommendations for future work include refining time-series clustering techniques, employing advanced data imputation and alternative signal representations, and further exploring reinforcement learning control strategies. These improvements could enhance automated diagnostics, leading to more robust, scalable, and data-centric approaches that will support the widespread adoption of efficient heat pump systems.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

Heat pumps are more energy-efficient and cleaner than gas and electric heaters, yet their adoption in private households is limited by high installation costs and uncertain running costs. Wider use of electrically operated heat pumps could help decarbonise heat, which currently accounts for one-third of UK carbon emissions.

Domestic heat pump performance varies considerably due to complex factors including design, installation, heating systems, and occupant behaviour. Typically, a professional is needed to assess and resolve underperformance (e.g. a coefficient of performance < 2.5). Automating the identification of performance issues could reduce expenses, promote broader adoption, and enable more robust estimates of through-life operating costs, thereby increasing homeowner confidence.

This DSG work represents an initial exploration into the level of automation possible and highlights promising directions for future research as well as current dataset limitations. The study uses the UK Electrification of Heat Trial dataset, which includes 2-minute resolution monitoring data from 740 UK home heat

Figure 1: Schematic of an air-source heat pump installation with sensors. Credit to Energy Systems Catapult

pump installations along with property characteristics, installation details, and demographic information. A schematic of an air-source heat pump and installed sensors is shown in Figure 1.

The challenge owner, ADViCE (AI for Decarbonisation Virtual Centre of Excellence), is a collaborative programme between Digital Catapult, Energy Systems Catapult, and The Alan Turing Institute. As part of the UK’s Department for Energy Security and Net Zero’s Innovation Portfolio, its goal is to develop innovative AI technologies for decarbonisation applications to support the transition to Net Zero. The DSG findings will be shared with ADViCE stakeholders to raise awareness of the dataset and demonstrate how AI and data-centric approaches can accelerate the energy transition.

2.1.1 Heat pump performance

The performance of a heat pump is typically calculated using a metric called the Coefficient of Performance (COP), which is defined as:

$$\text{COP} = \frac{\text{Heat Output of the Heat Pump}}{\text{Energy Consumed}} \quad (1)$$

COP can be calculated as an instantaneous measure, but it may also be averaged over a period of time, typically a whole season, which is known as a Seasonal

Performance Factor (SPF).

Different SPF measures exist depending on the system boundaries. For instance, SPFH1 only accounts for the power required by the heat pump and the heat it directly delivers, whereas SPFH4 includes all electricity-consuming equipment associated with the heat pump—such as back-up heaters, immersion heaters, and circulation pumps—as well as all their heat inputs.

2.2 DSG objectives

The challenge aims to use heat pump monitoring data to automatically identify issues affecting individual heat pump performance, especially those related to system configuration, installation quality, and control strategies. Identifying these issues automatically can reduce through-life heat pump costs by: (1) enabling owners to adjust configurations themselves; (2) providing timely alerts when underperformance is detected for faster resolution; and (3) helping technicians quickly diagnose the causes of underperformance.

These improvements could lead to more predictable operating costs and overall cost reductions, thereby encouraging homeowners to adopt less carbon-intensive heat pumps and supporting the decarbonisation of the heating industry.

More specifically, ADViCE is interested in exploring the following questions:

- Performance measurement
 - What is the best way to identify and compare periods of high and low performance both within and across heat pump installations?
- Installation-level indicators of poor performance
 - What property characteristics or aggregate statistics from each heat pump serve as risk factors for poor performance? Can system-level configuration (e.g. weather compensation curves) be used to predict poor performance?
- Time series symptoms of poor performance
 - What time series features/anomalies are associated with periods of poor performance?

- What time series features/anomalies are associated with low-performing heat pumps? Which are associated with high-performing heat pumps? How do they differ?
- How does the presence of certain features/anomalies affect performance over time? Which of these have the most significant effect on performance over time?
- Diagnosis
 - For a given set of detected anomalies in a heat pump dataset, what may be the possible causes?
 - Can certain issues be detected reliably? For example, heat pump cycling?

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

For this challenge we used a version of the Electrification of Heat dataset (collected 2020–2023), which includes 2-minute resolution monitoring data from 740 UK heat pump installations, along with property characteristics, installation details, and demographic information. This open-access dataset has been previously analyzed by Energy Systems Catapult and DESNZ. The dataset is structured as follows:

- A data dictionary for all variables.
- Time series data for each of the 740 installations, provided in CSV format (and in parquet for the large 2-minute resolution files). These files contain up to 3 years of data with up to 14 variables (e.g., timestamp, heat monitoring, internal/external temperature, energy input) and are organised into folders for 2-minute, 30-minute, and 1-day resolutions.
- Installation data in a single CSV file, with one row per installation capturing up to 128 quantitative and qualitative variables (e.g., property type, SAP score, total floor space, installation process, demographics, postcode, heat pump model).
- A dataset of summary statistics for each heat pump, including seasonal

performance factors, average COP, data quality scores, and data collection dates.

Additionally, there are two reports that examine (1) Participant recruitment processes and (2) Home surveys and installation data. These two reports are useful to understand how the data selection and collection process was carried out, as well as prior exploratory work conducted on the data.

3.2 Data quality

We conducted data quality checks following the guidelines in [10]:

- **Appropriateness:** The data is highly relevant for comparing heat pump performance and addressing the challenge questions.
- **Readiness:** A data dictionary and multiple reports on the data collection process were available, though no labelled data was provided, precluding supervised methods.
- **Reliability / Bias:** The dataset is based solely on UK home-installed heat pumps (installed between 2020 and 2021), which may not represent older or globally installed systems. Hardware and recruitment biases may also exist.
- **Sensitivity:** The data is openly available under an Open Government License 2.0.
- **Sufficiency:** The two-minute resolution data adequately captures detailed time-series changes and long collection periods reveal seasonal and daily patterns. However, the lack of labelled data limits supervised analyses.
- **Empty Data:** Common in the installation dataset, these instances were managed during sample selection and preprocessing.
- **Missingness and Completeness:** Missing data in both time-series and installation datasets, due to transmission issues or non-applicability, were addressed accordingly.

In addition to our analyses, the Catapult had previously assessed data quality. Based on discussions with the Challenge Owner, we used some of the Catapult's metrics and focused our efforts on unexplored aspects of data quality, enabling quicker progress to data exploration and challenge resolution.

3.3 Exploratory data analysis

The dataset contains 742 heat pumps (HP) of various types and makes, including low temperature air source heat pumps (LT ASHP), high temperature air source heat pumps (HT ASHP), ground source heat pumps (GSHP), and hybrid heat pumps (Hybrid HP). In this report, only heat pumps that had been considered by the Energy Systems Catapult for SPF analysis in the summary statistics dataset are included, as these heat pumps met the basic data quality criteria set out in the data quality report. This amounted to 545 heat pumps considered for analysis.

3.3.1 Heat pump types

Households were clustered based on heat pump technology, manufacturer, and nominal output (see Figure 2). Among the 545 households, 245 had LT ASHP, 183 had HT ASHP, 23 had GSHP, and 94 had Hybrid HP. ASHP are divided into low-temperature (LT) systems (max water temp $\sim 65^{\circ}\text{C}$) and high-temperature (HT) systems (up to $\sim 80^{\circ}\text{C}$, similar to gas boilers). LT ASHP are mainly from Daikin and Mitsubishi, while HT ASHP are predominantly Vaillant.

Notably, Daikin units typically use R410A refrigerant for LT and R32 refrigerant for HT, whereas about two-thirds of Mitsubishi units use R32—a newer, eco-friendlier refrigerant with improved efficiency. In terms of energy output, LT ASHP are usually in the 5–10 kW range, while HT ASHP span a broader spectrum, including several large units.

Figure 2: Heat pumps types across the dataset. Please note only the heat pumps included in the initial SPF analysis are presented.

3.3.2 Geographical coverage

Households were grouped into three clusters using district centroids (derived from the outward code, which is the first half of the postcode). Figure 3 shows heat pumps installed in South-East England (128), North-East England (309), and Central Belt Scotland (305), with one outlier in Inverness. In five households, an extra digit from the inward code (the second half of the postcode) was removed for consistency.

Figure 3: Geographical distribution of heat pumps, clustered in three zones: South-East England, North-East England, and Central Belt Scotland.

3.3.3 Factor analysis of installation data

The installation dataset includes 128 variables—both qualitative (e.g., employment status, property type) and quantitative (e.g., age, number of heated rooms). Variables were retained based on qualitative reasoning (e.g., keeping “Annual Electricity Usage” for its potential impact on heat pump usage), data type (excluding long texts or irrelevant dates), and sparsity (dropping variables with >20% missing values).

Missing values were handled as follows:

- Continuous numeric variables: imputed with the mean.
- Discrete numeric variables (e.g., number of children): imputed with the rounded mean or mode when appropriate.
- Categorical variables: imputed with the mode.

We applied Factor Analysis for Mixed Data (FAMD)—which combines PCA [2] for quantitative data and MCA [1] for qualitative data [11]—using the `FAMD()` function from the R packages `FactoMineR` and `factoextra`. The factors extracted via

FAMD would help describe the association between all variables, giving insights into which variables may be useful for further analyses. The scree plot in Figure 4 shows that the first principal component explains only about 3.4% of the variance, and the first four components together account for roughly 10%, highlighting the data's complexity and suggesting that one should think twice when considering to condense the data into a lower-dimensional space.

Figure 4: Scree plot for the Factor Analysis

Figures 5a and 5b show the top 15 contributing variables for the first two components, mostly reflecting heat pump and geographical information. The score plot in Figure 6 (with heat pumps coloured by SPF: blue for SPF > 2.5, red for SPF < 2.5) suggests that higher-SPF heat pumps tend to associate positively with the first factor, although the low variance explained advises caution in interpretation.

(a) The top 15 contributing factors of the first principal component

(b) The top 15 contributing factors of the second principal component

Figure 5: Top 15 contributing factors of the first two principal components

Figure 6: Score plot for the 545 heat pumps

4 Scientific approach

After considering the challenge objectives, the team split into two task groups: one focused on identifying symptoms of underperformance from time-series data and the other on analysing performance based on installation data. The overall strategy is summarised in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Research strategy followed by the team

4.1 Time-series data analysis

The hypothesis was that low-performing heat pumps exhibit different time-series patterns than high-performing ones, and that these patterns can be captured via

feature extraction and clustering. If robust patterns are identified, they can later be labelled by heat pump professionals to enable supervised diagnosis. Figure 8 shows an example pattern for a low-performing unit.

The subgroup explored the following research questions:

- Can clustering of features extracted from time series differentiate high-performing from low-performing heat pumps?
- Do clusters correspond to similar COP values?
- Is cycling frequency in flow temperature directly related to performance?
- Can underperformance be explained by degradation of performance over time?

The team was further divided into two smaller groups: one focused on directly clustering peaks and cycles (using Empirical Mode Decomposition + K-means and z-score peak transformation + Dynamic Time Warping), and the other on clustering extracted features (primarily based on HP electricity consumption due to time constraints). A common dataset sample was used (details in Section 5.1), and unsupervised methods were applied due to the lack of labelled data.

Finally, another line of work explored whether the low performance of some heat pumps could be explained by an accelerated degradation of performance over time, compared to high-performing heat pumps.

Figure 8: Example of discernible operational pattern for a low-performing heat pump, exhibiting a repeating pattern of sharp temperature peaks over a 36-hour period. Legend: Red - HP flow temperature [Celsius], Green - HP return temperature [Celsius], Purple - Outside temperature [Celsius], Black - Inside temperature [Celsius], Yellow - Heat input power [W], Blue - Heat pump electricity consumption [W], DHW - Domestic water heating cycle

4.2 Installation data analysis

The installation data analysis group hypothesised that certain property characteristics and system-level configurations serve as risk factors for poor performance. They addressed the following questions:

- What property characteristics or aggregate statistics predict poor performance?
- Can system-level configuration be used to predict poor performance?
- Do causal relationships exist between installation features and heat pump performance?

A common dataset sample was used (see Section 6.1). Two approaches were explored:

- A non-linear regression model using CatBoost and SHAP for feature interpretation, leveraging CatBoost's efficient handling of categorical data and SHAP's explainability.
- A cross-sectional linear regression model using a small set of variables (technical specifications, building characteristics, and installation quality)

estimated sequentially to test their incremental contribution.

Additionally, a causal discovery algorithm (the Peter-Clark algorithm [14]) was implemented to graph the causal relationships between installation features and performance. The objective was to go beyond the predictions and correlations previously identified by the Mixed Data Factor Analysis and CatBoost [12] to reveal actual causes of underperformance and intuitively represent them.

4.3 Reinforcement learning-based adaptive control strategy

An exploratory study also assessed whether a reinforcement learning-based control strategy could outperform traditional rule-based weather compensation in maintaining target indoor temperatures. This investigation focused on the RL agent’s learning behaviour, convergence speed, and overall performance. Results demonstrate that the RL agent was able to maintain the indoor temperature close to a target of 21°C. The total episode rewards are stable across the different episodes, which indicates that the strategy learned by the agent is consistent across different scenarios. However, further refinements are needed to enhance robustness and efficiency. Results of this study are presented in detail in Appendix G.

5 Time-series symptoms of underperformance

5.1 Sample selection

Following discussions with the CO and a heat pump expert, we decided to focus on **air-source heat pumps (ASHPs)** for the remainder of the challenge, particularly for time-series analysis, and dropping ground-source and hybrid heat pumps. This is because GSHPs and Hybrid HPs are known to exhibit very different performance patterns to ASHPs, which would have made analysis too unwieldy. Furthermore, there is proportionally a much larger number of ASHP installations, as evidenced by Figure 2. The following subsections describe the further refinement and definition of our sample.

5.1.1 Geographical distribution

For ASHPs, Figures 9a and 9b display their distribution by type. LT ASHP are evenly spread, while HT ASHP are under-represented in South-East England. In summary, South-East England has 78 LT ASHP and 7 HT ASHP, North-East England 52 LT ASHP and 66 HT ASHP, and Central Belt Scotland 115 LT ASHP and 110 HT ASHP.

Figure 9: Geographical distribution of air source heat pumps (low and high temperature) included in the study.

5.1.2 Outdoor & Indoor temperatures

Daily minimum, average, and maximum outdoor temperatures were computed from 2-minute interval data for each household and compared across the three installation locations. Indoor temperatures were also analysed, revealing a slight variability due to differing homeowner practices. On average, Central Belt Scotland recorded the lowest indoor temperatures, while North-East England had the highest (see Figure 10). Outdoor temperatures are nearly identically distributed across all geographies. COP is directly related to indoor and outdoor temperature, but these results suggest that geographical location would not be a strong confounder. These results are further validated by the Factor Analysis of Mixed Data performed in Section 3.3.3.

Figure 10: Indoor and outdoor temperature ranges across the LT ASHP for the three regions.

5.1.3 Performance differences between high-temperature and low-temperature air-source heat pumps

To decide whether to analyse both groups together or focus solely on low-temperature heat pumps, we compared their SPF values. Figure 11 shows the SPF distributions, which were tested for normality using the Lilliefors test[3]. The low-temperature group had a p-value of 0.104, while the high-temperature group had a p-value of 0.001, indicating non-normality for the latter. Consequently, we applied the Mann-Whitney U test, yielding a p-value of 0.008, which confirms a significant performance difference. A complementary z-test on the means ($p = 0.004$) supports this result. Since LT ASHPs have a lower SCOP overall, and hence more potential for improvement, and considering LT ASHPs are the most common among ASHP configurations, we selected LT ASHPs as our subset. Thus, our subsequent analysis will focus on **LT ASHPs**.

5.1.4 LT ASHP household data

Out of 235 properties with LT ASHP (with at least 22 months of data ending near 2023-09-28), preliminary analysis shows a clear seasonal drop in COP. For example, Property EOH0102 (Figure 12) exhibits a COP of around 2–2.5 in winter, compared to peak values of approximately 3.7 in summer and 3.5 in spring. This seasonal variation, coupled with the fact that all heat pumps operate in heating mode during winter (unlike in summer), that it is more likely that heat pumps will

Figure 11: The distributions of SPF values for low-temperature (left) and high-temperature (right) heat pumps

not be used at all during summer, justifies focusing our performance analysis on winter data.

Figure 12: 12-week 2-minute 24-hour seasonal COP of the Property: EOH0102.

5.1.5 LT ASHP winter data availability and COP

Data availability was evaluated for winters 2020–2021, 2021–2022, and 2022–2023 (defined from 1 December to the last day of February, with leap years accounted for). As shown in Table 1, the 2022–2023 winter had the highest completeness and lowest missingness, making it the optimal period for further analysis.

Year	Completeness (%)	Missingness (%)
2020-2021	96.1	<0.1
2021-2022	99.4	0.6
2022-2023	99.7	0.3

Table 1: Evaluation of missingness and completeness for three winter periods.

Figure 13: Boxplot of seasonal COP - LT ASHP of 156 properties.

Out of 235 LT ASHP properties, 156 have sufficient winter data (1 December 2022–1 March 2023). Figure 36 (Appendix) displays the 2-minute 24-hour COP for 10 properties, where most values range from 2 to 3, with one property as low as 1–1.5. The box plot in Figure 13 shows a median winter COP of approximately 2.8 — slightly lower than in spring and summer.

We use this subset of 156 properties for time-series analysis. We decided not to split further by manufacturer + refrigerant to understand whether common patterns across all LT HPs could be observed.

In summary, we restrict our analysis to the following scope of data:

- (a) Low-Temperature Air Source Heat Pumps (ASHP)
- (b) At least one year of usable data/ data available
- (c) The SPF is within the range 1.25 to 5.5
 - The SPF boundaries were chosen based on a range of factors to ensure that the heat pumps selected show realistic performances. More details can be found at Heat Pump Performance Data Analysis Report
- (d) The maximum data quality score in the SPF window is less than 4
 - More details about data scoring can be found at Heat Pump Performance Data Analysis Report

5.1.6 Data preprocessing steps previously conducted by the Electrification of Heat team

In addition to the data preprocessing steps followed in this report, the EoH team previously carried out several data preprocessing and cleaning steps on the raw data. These steps are detailed in their data quality report, but the main steps followed included:

- Timestamp alignment to exact 2-minute periods;
- Cumulative meter data reversals;
- Anomalous cumulative data removal – single point;
- Anomalous cumulative data removal – from start of monitoring;
- Re-levelling data following a meter reset;
- Incorrect column assignment for non-cumulative (temperature) data;
- Removal of out-of-range temperatures;
- Supplementary data cleansing – amending spelling or grammar variations;
- Supplementary data cleansing – aligning property age ranges.

5.2 Approach 1: Direct clustering of peaks and cycles

There are inherent challenges associated with identifying peaks or cycles within a time series, especially one with an abundance of noise and missing values. Our aim in this subsection is to estimate the frequency of cycling in heat pumps, and then

- associate the cycling frequencies/peak patterns to the HPs' SPF or COP performances,
- cluster the heat pumps based on their cycling patterns.

To achieve the goals above, it is necessary to devise (or use) a peak/cycle finding algorithm that picks up instances of “volatile” changes in a time series, but should avoid being so overly sensitive that it picks up random noise in the data.

The team experimented with two peak finding algorithms: empirical model decomposition and z-score peak transformation.

5.2.1 Empirical mode decomposition with K-means

EMD decomposes a time series into intrinsic mode functions (IMFs) that capture natural oscillations—each IMF having equal numbers of extrema and zero-crossings and being symmetric around a local mean [6]. For example, using a 24-hour window from heat pump EOH0793 (Figure 14), we observed cycling behaviour with distinct peaks corresponding to domestic hot water usage.

A baseline method is to use SciPy's `find_peaks()` function (with parameters like `width`, `threshold`, `distance`, and `prominence`) to detect cycles. However, generalisation of this method would be challenging as each time series would require specific tuning to achieve good peak extraction.

Alternatively, we applied EMD via the Python EMD package with a mask sift. Figure 15 displays the nine IMFs extracted; IMF-1 captures minute fluctuations (noise), while IMF-2 and IMF-3 best represent the overall structure. We then superimposed selected IMFs (either IMF-2 to IMF-9 or IMF-3 to IMF-9) and applied our one-dimensional peak finding algorithm (Appendix C). This approach yielded 74 peaks for the IMF-2–IMF-9 superposition and 56 peaks for IMF-3–IMF-9 (Figure 16), demonstrating reasonable alignment with visual inspection.

However, the EMD was not too robust across time series with varying pulse lengths and missing meter readings. For some heat pumps (e.g., EOH0516), we

Figure 14: Heat Pump Energy Output for EOH0793 from 2022-12-05 00:00:00 to 2022-12-06 00:00:00

used only IMF-6 to IMF-9 to avoid capturing minor spikes, while for others (e.g., EOH0889, EOH1249) IMF-3 to IMF-9 provided a better reconstruction. Future work may benefit from adaptive models to improve robustness across diverse time series.

K-Means clustering of features generated from EMD We extracted flow temperature time-series data from 156 air source heat pumps on 5th Dec 2022, applying forward/backward filling to handle missing data. Fourteen heat pumps were removed because their signals lacked variance, leaving 142 for analysis. For each, we applied the EMD algorithm to extract 6 IMFs and computed six features per IMF: mean value, standard deviation, skewness (using `skew()` from `scipy.stats`), kurtosis (using `kurtosis()` from `scipy.stats`), peak-to-peak distance, and the number of peaks. Since the top IMFs mostly captured noise, we focused on the third IMF. Figure 17a shows that while most features were weakly correlated, the peak-to-peak distance was highly correlated with standard deviation, and kurtosis was positively correlated with both.

We then used K-Means clustering (with $k = 3$, yielding a silhouette score of 0.458) on these features, with an 80/20 train/test split. Feature contributions—calculated from the variance of centroid values—indicated that peak-to-peak distance and standard deviation were the most influential, followed by skewness and kurtosis (Figure 17b).

Figure 15: The Intrinsic Mode Functions of EMD performed on the heat pump output energy

To improve performance of the k-means clustering approach, future work should consider extending the window of time-series data used in our analysis, since we were constrained to a single day of time-series data due to computational and time constraints. Further improvements may be possible through the exploration of alternative approaches for extracting the frequency components of the time-series signals, such as the Fast Fourier Transform, since we observed that fixed choices of IMF (e.g. always selecting the second, third, and fourth IMFs) to represent the time series exhibited variable performance in representing the useful signal in the time-series data. Alternatively, methods for dynamically selecting IMFs could also be considered. Finally, further work may be explored regarding the features extracted from the time-series data, as measures such as skewness and kurtosis consider the overall time series and its closeness to a normal distribution. An alternative approach to consider could be to use the skewness and kurtosis of individual peaks as a feature for future work, as it could provide more informative

Figure 16: The superimposed IMFs and the original time series with peaks identified

and granular information about the nature of the peaks themselves within the time series. The peaks could be extracted using a z-score based algorithm (see next section).

5.2.2 Z-Score peak transformation with dynamic time warping K-means

Clustering 24-hour time traces of flow temperature on the same day for different properties turned out to be challenging due to the sheer diversity of graphs. We therefore tried to simplify the clustering task by isolating individual pulses of around an hour rather than the full day.

To isolate individual pulses, we required a robust and flexible algorithm capable of reliably identifying pulses of various shapes. We chose a z-score-based algorithm

(a) The correlation heat map of the features extracted from the IMF3

(b) Feature contribution to the KMeans Clustering over the IMF3 from the EMD algorithm

Figure 17: Correlation heat map and feature contributions for IMF3

[5]. The algorithm is based on the principle of "dispersion": it keeps track

of a moving average and standard deviation in a sliding window and measures how far new points deviate from the expected mean signal. The number of standard deviations by which the new point deviates is called its "z-score". Key hyperparameters include:

- **Lag:** Length of the time window for which the moving average and standard deviation are calculated (values of 5 worked best).
- **Influence** (between 0 and 1): Weight of past pulses on the detection threshold (values near 0 worked best). If the influence is 0 then past pulses do not influence the detection threshold. If it is 0.5 then pulses have half as much influence as normal data points
- **Threshold:** Number of standard deviations above the moving mean (set at 2 as it seemed to capture peaks best).

Pulses are defined as a peak followed by a trough. For LT ASHPs on 12th December 2022, only peaks with durations between 1–2 hours were retained and downsampled from 2880 to 500 peaks for computational feasibility.

Clustering of individual peaks Clustering time series requires a distance metric that can handle traces of different lengths and pulse periods. Euclidean distance falls short because it fails to capture similar shapes with varying durations. Instead, Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [7] is better suited as it aligns signals by matching peaks to peaks and troughs to troughs, regardless of period differences. However, caution is needed when signals end in different phases, as DTW might misalign these endpoints and inflate the calculated distance. Two DTW clustering algorithms were compared:

- **DBA k-means:** Minimises the sum of squared DTW distances between the barycenter and each series.
- **SDTW k-means:** Minimises a weighted sum of soft DTW distances.

Figures 19 and 20 present clusters for $k = 2$ and $k = 5$, each annotated with average COP values, silhouette scores, and ANOVA p-values to confirm significant differences between clusters. We used silhouette scores—ranging from -1 to 1—for an objective quality assessment (see Figure 38), as this method is less heuristic than the elbow method. Overall, SDTW k-means outperformed DBA k-means, achieving best scores of 0.477 for $k = 2$ and 0.421 for $k = 5$; the two-cluster solution

(a) Property EOH0067

(b) Property EOH0073

Figure 18: Examples of results from z-score algorithm. The orange step function takes a value of 1 at peaks and -1 at troughs but has been magnified for the visualisation.

primarily differentiates average flow temperature, while the five-cluster solution

reveals more diverse signal shapes.

In the future, a more rigorous association of pulse shape with performance would require: the precise fine-tuning of lag, influence and threshold for the z-score algorithm with heat pump domain knowledge so as to capture pulses very accurately. The choice of pulse duration is also crucial. Increasing computational resources would allow a speed-up of SDTW k-means and thus the inclusion of more peaks, leading to better clusters. Finally, the average pulse shapes of these clusters could then be associated with good and bad performance and other heat pump behaviour, which would allow faster automated diagnosis of issues in the future.

Figure 19: DBA and Soft DTW clustering for $k = 2$

Figure 20: DBA and Soft DTW clustering for $k = 5$

5.3 Approach 2: Clustering of features extracted from time-series

5.3.1 Feature extraction

Power consumption features

Although the dataset contains information including flow temperatures and energy consumption, in any scalable and/or Predictive Maintenance (PdM) scenario, it is expected that only electricity consumption data will be available either through the smart metering infrastructure (through disaggregation) or directly through an API that directly connects to the HP. A hypothesis is made that with the use of only the electricity consumption data, under-performing HPs can be identified. In order to uncover underlying issues related to the operation of HPs, such as badly set weather compensation curves, only through the usage of electricity consumption data, several features were extracted from the given time series.

Features related to each individual active and idle window of each HP were extracted. More specifically, the following features were extracted:

- The length of each individual activation and idle window [mins]
- The average power level of each activation window [W]
- The energy consumption in each activation window [Wh]
- The intensity level of the activation window compared to the nominal power of the HP [%]

Figure 21 summarises the features that were extracted intra-daily from the activation windows.

Figure 21: Extracted features sample.

Further to these features, the following daily features were extracted from the 245 LT ASHP.

- Number of activation (pulses) of the HP
- The intensity level of the HP compared to the nominal power [%]
- The daily minimum, maximum, average, and median of the pulses' duration [mins]
- The daily minimum, maximum, average, and median of the pulses' energy [Wh]
- The daily minimum, maximum, average, and median of the pulses' intensity compared to the nominal power [%]
- The daily minimum, maximum, average, and median of the pulses' average power level [W]

- Number of idle windows of the HP
- The daily minimum, maximum, average, and median of the idle windows' duration [mins]
- The “active” period of the HP [%]

Weather compensation curves Weather compensation adjusts the water flow temperature of a heat pump based on the external air temperature. The hypothesis is that a well-configured system will exhibit a strong linear correlation between external temperature and flow temperature, ensuring higher flow temperatures on very cold days (for adequate heating) and lower ones on milder days (to boost COP).

To test this, we compared two Vaillant models over a representative winter month (12-01-2023 to 12-02-2023), shown in Figure 22. The high-performing unit (property ID 2686, SPFH4=4.08) displayed a fairly linear relationship ($R^2=0.492$) between external and flow temperatures, while the low-performing unit (property ID 0144, SPFH4=1.91) did not. The analysis also incorporated the theoretical weather compensation curves for Vaillant heat pumps.

Before analysis, flow temperature data were filtered to remove periods when the heat pump was non-operational, during a DHW cycle, and the two minutes immediately after a DHW cycle (as illustrated in Figure 44 in the Appendix).

(a) High-performing Vaillant HP with SPF_{H4} of 4.08. (b) Low-performing Vaillant HP with SPF_{H4} of 1.91.

Figure 22: Scatter plots of flow temperature (y) and outside temperature (x) with a linear regression fit on time series data from 12-01-2023 to 12-02-2023. The continuous lines represent the Vaillant weather compensation curves, taken from Vaillant website.

5.3.2 K-means clustering of the features

We applied K-means clustering on the power consumption features previously extracted from LT ASHP data for the 24-hour period on 12th December 2022. The features used were:

- Percentage_On
- Percentage_Max_Power_On
- Number_Of_Pulses
- Number_Of_Idle
- Avg_Pulse_Duration
- Avg_Pulse_Energy
- Avg_Pulse_Fullness

- Avg_Pulse_AveragePower
- Avg_Idle

Due to data quality and availability considerations, the sample was narrowed down to 139 heat pumps. Clustering these into $k = 2$ clusters yielded two groups (85 and 54 heat pumps). Figure 23 visualises the clustering patterns: the blue cluster (85 heat pumps) generally shows fewer pulses (≤ 25 per day) and higher values (and variability) in average pulse duration, fullness, percentage maximum power on, and energy, whereas the red cluster exhibits more pulses with lower values for these features.

Given that the data are unlabelled, we also used a naive classifier that designates heat pumps with $\text{COP} > 2.5$ as high-performing and those with $\text{COP} < 2.5$ as low-performing. After discarding a further 8 heat pumps without COP data, visualisations for 131 heat pumps (Figure 24) reveal markedly different behaviour between the naïve clusters and the power consumption-based clusters, which suggests that the power consumption features may be insufficient and require further processing. Figure 37 (Appendix) further compares COP against each extracted feature, indicating that heat pumps with an unusually high number of pulses tend to have lower to moderate COP values.

Figure 23: Scatterplots showing the relationships between the features and the clusters. Red represents cluster 1, blue represents cluster 2

Figure 24: Comparison of clustering based on power consumption features (left column: Red for cluster 1 and blue for cluster 2) vs a naive classifier (right column: purple for COP > 2.5, orange for COP < 2.5)

5.3.3 Relationship between weather compensation curve R^2 value and heat pump performance

For the R^2 vs. COP analysis, we considered 156 LT heat pumps over the winter period from 01-12-2022 to 01-03-2023.

The results revealed no clear positive correlation between the R^2 values and COP; in fact, a slight negative trend was observed. This suggests that R^2 alone may not reliably indicate a properly configured weather compensation curve. One explanation is that some high-performing heat pumps are set to maintain a fixed flow temperature (appropriate for well-insulated homes), thereby decoupling the expected linear relationship with external temperature. Although our figures mostly depict Vaillant models, the overall principles of weather compensation remain applicable across different heat pump brands.

Figure 25: Relationship between COP and R^2 of flow temperature vs external temperature over the time window 01-12-22 to 01-03-23 for the selected 156 LT heat pumps.

5.4 Approach 3: Degradation of COP over time

This analysis investigated whether long-term performance degradation—potentially due to debris accumulation and compressor wear [4]—drives heat pump underperformance. We compared the daily COP_{H2} (defined as Energy Output divided by Energy Consumed) over the 2021–2023 period for the bottom and top 25% of LT ASHPs.

Key processing steps included:

- Converting cumulative energy data to daily values by differencing, then handling missing values and outliers: Five properties with extreme COP_{H2} values (outside the 1.5 IQR range) were dropped, and remaining outliers were set to missing and forward filled over up to 5 days. Properties with too many missing values after this stage were removed from the analysis, leaving 101 properties.
- Smoothing COP_{H2} using a 10-day rolling average (where there are at least three values per 10-day window) to mitigate missing data issues without disrupting seasonal patterns. Observations where the rolling average is

missing were dropped

- Applying Fast Fourier Transform to extract dominant seasonal components, then decomposing each time series into trend, seasonal, and residual components.
- Fitting a linear trend to the rolling average and extracting its slope as the daily degradation rate.

Results showed a daily degradation rate of -0.000215 for low performers versus -0.000411 for high performers, translating to approximately -0.15 and -0.29 COP_{H2} over two years. A Welch's t-test ($p = 0.2374$) indicated no statistically significant difference in degradation rates between the groups. This suggests that no statistically significant difference exists in the rate of degradation between low and top performing ASHPs.

Figure 26: This graph compares the distribution in the daily coefficients of degradation of COP_{H2} over time between the bottom 25% and top 25% low-temperature ASHPs.

This result may be further illustrated in Figure 26, which plots the daily coefficients of degradation for both the low and top-performing ASHPs in our sample. While the median of the underperforming group is slightly closer to 0, their distributions match closely one another. Despite these results, further work is required to fully ascertain whether performance degradation due to heat pump wear is a significant driver of underperformance. We discuss these in the following paragraph.

Limitations and future work One issue with this method is that the trend in COP_{H2} itself is correlated with the trend in outside temperature. Therefore, even if you remove seasonal and residual components, if year 2 was colder on average than year 1, COP_{H2} will experience a drop, which may not necessarily be due to degradation of the heat pump itself. Therefore, to really determine whether a heat pump has degraded, we need a robust method to control for weather trends. One possible approach could be to build a table of expected COPs for different external temperatures during year 1, so that performance across a range of temperatures can be observed over time.

6 Causal inference and analysis of performance based on installation data

6.1 Sample selection

The data considered by this team considers properties for which SPF analysis was conducted by Energy Systems Catapult, as otherwise, analyses which rely on heat pump performance would not be possible. A total of 545 properties are selected for the analysis to ensure a large sample size to improve the robustness of our findings. In this case, a wide range of building characteristics, including different sizes and ages, are covered to reflect the variety of residential properties where heat pumps are installed.

6.2 Approach 1: Non-linear analysis on installation data

We explore the relationship between installation data and heat pump performance using a non-linear regression model, with SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) values for feature interpretation (see Figure 27). To manage over 100 variables, we first preprocessed the data by removing irrelevant columns (e.g., constant values,

date fields, free-text responses) and standardising entries (correcting typos and inconsistencies, such as changing "carer" to "career" and changing "Prefer not to say" to "Unknown"). Missing values were imputed with the mean for numerical features and replaced with "Unknown" for categorical ones.

Figure 27: Workflow for Non-linear analysis on Installation Data

We then applied the CatBoost model, which we selected for its efficient handling of categorical data without the need for complex encoding. SHAP was used to clearly identify which features have the greatest impact on heat pump performance.

Results We assessed the importance of various installation factors for predicting SPFH4 using SHAP values (see Figures 39 (in Appendix) and 28). The top 15 influential features are shown in 2. HP_Brand ranks highest, indicating that the brand (and its associated efficiency and installation quality) most significantly impacts performance, while variables like EmployType and Total.Floor.Area highlight the roles of socioeconomic and building characteristics.

Feature	Feature Importance
HP_Brand	6.49
MCS_SHAnnual	4.51
EmployType	3.99
EstCost_Running	3.67
Total_Floor_Area	2.82
Cost_TS	2.62
Reason_Future	2.56
Cost_Emitters	2.50
House_SAP	2.41
Cost_HP	2.40
House_Age	2.38
MCS_Hloss	2.29
MCS_SCOP	2.21
MCS_DHWAnnual	2.09
Participant_Age	2.04

Table 2: Feature Importance for SPFH4_selected_window. Larger SHAP absolute values represent a stronger effect on model output. Positive values represent a magnitude increase in model output. Negative values represent a magnitude decrease in model output.

Discussion and limitations The SHAP values obtained suggest no strong association between installation features and heat pump performance. Possible reasons for the lack of strong associations could be the high cardinality in some variables, and potentially the data imputation approach, which involved assigning missing values to the mode, which could have significantly skewed the sample. For data imputation, more advanced approaches could be attempted, such as random forests and multiple imputation, which may reduce these issues: Random forest imputation uses decision trees to predict missing values iteratively by modelling complex variable relationships from observed data [15]. Multiple imputation repeatedly fills in missing data via statistical models, generating several complete datasets, whose results are combined to reflect uncertainty [9].

Figure 28: SHAP Value Impact on SPFH4 Prediction

6.3 Approach 2: Causal analysis

Drawing from the insights of earlier sections on the installation features most predictive of performance, the team implemented a causal discovery algorithm intended to graph the causal relationships between installation features and heat pump performance. To this end, the team used the Peter-Clark (PC) algorithm—a

constraint-based causal discovery method—to uncover causal relationships between installation features and heat pump performance beyond correlations [14]. Because the PC algorithm cannot handle mixed data types, it was applied in two ways:

- **Discrete Features:** Implemented on all 545 heat pumps using a G-squared test for independence capable of handling low-frequency categories.
- **Continuous Features:** Applied on 235 LT ASHPs using the RCIT test of independence capable of identifying non linear relationships. It is important to note that this algorithm was reduced to LT ASHPs in an effort to prevent confounding that may result from being unable to control for the type of heat pump since the continuous feature set may not include the heat pump model or type.

The PC algorithm builds a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) by first constructing a fully connected undirected graph, then iteratively removing edges based on independence tests, identifying collider structures (which may be understood as any structure $A - C - B$, where A and B are dependent only when conditioning on C . In this case, the algorithm orients the edges as $A \rightarrow C \leftarrow B$), and propagating edge directions while ensuring acyclicity and respecting collider structures.

The DAG from the discrete feature set (Figure 29) reveals intuitive relationships, such as Emitter System Cost being influenced by House Age and Installation Cost—but shows that Heat Pump Performance (SPFH4) remains isolated. The analysis on the continuous features supports this finding (Figure 30).

Overall, the causal discovery approach suggests that when controlling for potential confounders, none of the installation features, however predictive of the outcome they may be, seem to be causally related to heat pump performance.

6.4 Approach 3: Cross-sectional regression model

We examine heat pump performance (measured by SPFH4) through three cross-sectional regression models that sequentially incorporate up to three sets of features:

- **Technical Specifications:** These include measures of flow temperature and system sizing. Specifically, we use the mean annual flow temperature (with an indicator variable for temperatures above 45°C), nominal heat pump size,

Figure 29: DAG graph of the PC algorithm fit on the discrete features set with 545 heat pumps. The algorithm uses the G-squared test of independence and a statistical significance level of 0.1. Only interconnected features are displayed for clarity.

Figure 30: DAG graph of the PC algorithm fit on the continuous features set of 235 ASHP. The algorithm uses the RCIT test of independence and a statistical significance level of 0.1. Only interconnected features are displayed for clarity.

size normalised per floor area (W/m^2), and a binary indicator for over-sizing (i.e., if the system exceeds 100 W/m^2).

- **Building Characteristics:** These include the total floor area and house type (with Detached as the reference category). An interaction term between flow temperature and floor area is used to capture potential moderation effects of building size.
- **Installation Quality:** This construct is measured by the installation time (in hours) and a commissioning quality score.

The models are estimated sequentially: Model 1 includes only technical specification variables; Model 2 adds building characteristics; and Model 3 adds installation quality variables. This sequential (hierarchical) approach allows us to test whether each set of variables significantly improves the explanation of SPFH4 performance. Table 3 presents the results of each regression model, with the results of each model corresponding to each column in the table (column (1) corresponds to Model 1, column (2) to Model 2, and column (3) to Model (3))

Our hypotheses were:

1. Technical specifications (flow temperature and system sizing) significantly affect heat pump SPFH4 performance.
2. Building characteristics (floor area and house type) significantly influence SPFH4 performance beyond technical effects.
3. Installation quality (installation time and commissioning) significantly impact SPFH4 performance after controlling for technical and building characteristics.

Discussion and implications Hierarchical regression results support the hypotheses (see Table 3). Model 1 shows that lower flow temperatures and proper system sizing enhance SPFH4. Model 2's inclusion of building characteristics boosts explanatory power (Adjusted R^2 from 0.096 to 0.132), with floor area positively associated, and the negative interaction term (Flow Temp \times Floor Area) suggests that larger properties experience a more detrimental effect from high flow temperature. Model 3 further improves performance prediction (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.144$), with a significant negative effect for poor commissioning quality.

	<i>Dependent variable: SPFH4_selected_window</i>		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Flow Temp × Floor Area		-1.320*** (0.374)	-1.292*** (0.372)
Heat Pump Size (kW)	0.250*** (0.048)	-0.090 (0.157)	-0.028 (0.158)
High Flow Temp (>45°C)	-0.063 (0.055)	-0.076 (0.055)	-0.073 (0.055)
House Type: End-Terrace		-0.211 (0.156)	-0.164 (0.156)
House Type: Flat		0.109 (0.220)	0.015 (0.258)
House Type: Mid-Terrace		-0.359** (0.148)	-0.340** (0.147)
House Type: Semi-Detached		-0.253** (0.101)	-0.220** (0.101)
Installation Time (hours)			0.042 (0.051)
Commissioning Quality Score			-0.131*** (0.043)
Flow Temperature (°C)	-0.121** (0.055)	0.268** (0.125)	0.263** (0.124)
Oversized System (>100 W/m ²)	-0.236*** (0.059)	-0.227*** (0.060)	-0.203*** (0.060)
Size per Floor Area (W/m ²)	0.075 (0.065)	0.335** (0.142)	0.223 (0.146)
Floor Area (m ²)		1.481*** (0.405)	1.396*** (0.404)
Intercept	0.000 (0.041)	0.135** (0.066)	0.122* (0.066)
Observations	544	544	544
R ²	0.104	0.149	0.164
Adjusted R ²	0.096	0.132	0.144
Residual Std. Error	0.951 (df=538)	0.932 (df=532)	0.925 (df=530)
F Statistic	12.490*** (df=5; 538)	8.477*** (df=11; 532)	8.004*** (df=13; 530)

Table 3: Cross-sectional Regression Analysis. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. Standard errors in parentheses. All continuous variables are standardised (mean=0, std=1). House types are dummy variables with Detached as reference category. High Flow Temp is a binary indicator for flow temperatures above 45°C. Oversized System indicates heat pump size > 100 W/m² of floor area.

These results suggest that:

- Optimising technical design, especially flow temperature control and system sizing, is critical.
- Integrating building-specific features is important since larger buildings are more adversely affected by high flow temperatures.

- Investing in high-quality installation and commissioning can significantly boost performance.

7 Discussion and limitations

The approaches followed for direct time-series clustering showed promise in extracting interpretable time-series patterns from high-performing and low-performing heat pumps. The Z-Score peak finding + SDTW K-means clustering was particularly promising, seeming more robust than DBA K-means and EMD + K-means approach, achieving silhouette scores of 0.477 for $k=2$ and 0.421 for $k=5$. However, due to time constraints the team was not able to fine-tune the hyperparameters of SDTW K-means, which may have improved results.

Unfortunately, clustering based on extracted features were less conclusive, both for power consumption data and weather compensation curves. Since we observe no significant relationships between COP and any of the time series features, there is reason to believe that our methodologies may be lacking in terms of robustness and their abilities to deal with sparse data.

A possible explanation for the inconclusive results is that our models were trained and tested over a single day of data due to computational capacity constraints, which means that the effect of any spurious operational patterns that day would have skewed the results. Training over longer time windows may help mitigate this effect and improve clustering performance.

The non-linear and causal analyses of installation data suggest (1) no strong association between any variable and SPFH4, and (2) no causal relationship between any of the variables and performance. Possible reasons for the lack of strong associations could be the high cardinality in some variables, and potentially the data imputation approach, which involved assigning missing values to the mode, which could have significantly skewed the sample. For data imputation, more advanced approaches could be attempted, such as random forests and multiple imputation. Additionally, for the causal discovery algorithms, some of the assumptions made include the Causal Markov Condition [8], Faithfulness (or Stability) Assumption [17], and Causal Sufficiency [18] which may not always be satisfied. Moreover, there is some randomness to the process of the PC algorithm which may result in slightly different structures

across iterations.

Conversely, the linear cross-sectional regression analysis shows a statistically significant association between variables such as type of house, commissioning quality score, and floor area with performance. Interestingly, floor area presents a strong positive relationship with performance, which may mean that larger houses are likely to be better insulated.

The reinforcement learning-based control strategy shows promising early results, but further fine-tuning of control policies is required. For example, the current control policy that only allows switching fully on or off and is rewarded for maintaining temperature may lead to high-frequency on/off cycles once it converges to the target temperature, which could place undue stress on heat pump components.

8 Conclusion and future work

Work on this challenge sought to address the challenge of automatically identifying symptoms of underperformance using heat pump monitoring and installation data. The results of approaches attempted in this challenge show promise, but the computational, time-related, and data cleaning challenges experienced suggest that a larger and more concerted effort is required to more systematically explore the potential of data-driven approaches to address the challenge.

Future work could focus on fine-tuning time-series clustering approaches already attempted in this report and exploring other more advanced data imputation methods for installation data. Alternative time-series representation methods, such as Discrete Wavelet Transform, different distance measurements, such as KL-distances, and other clustering algorithms, such as Bayesian hierarchical clustering, or deep time series clustering, could be considered. In this report, we sought to find common patterns across all LT ASHPs, but further splitting according to HP model and configuration may make the clustering more robust, as different heat pump models are known in the industry to have different operational patterns.

9 Team members

Yujie Dai is a PhD student at the Centre of Doctoral Training in Digital Health and Care, University of Bristol, England, UK, specialising in real-world complex health data analysis and infectious diseases diagnosis with AI techniques. She has an MSc in AI from the University of St Andrews, Scotland and a BSc in Software Engineering from the Beijing Institute of Technology, China. She contributed to this project by data quality check, data correlation and description analysis, and time-series data clustering.

Chakron Dechkrut is a PhD student in Civil Engineering at the School of Energy, Geoscience, Infrastructure and Society, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, Scotland, specialising in the application of machine learning in structural engineering problems. He holds an MSc in Structural Engineering from the University of Sheffield. He contributed to this project by doing exploratory data analysis in LT ASHP Household Data, Winter data availability, providing insights into seasonality HPs performance analysis, and presenting data overview and exploratory data analysis.

Aidan Kelly is a data scientist at Nesta, an innovation agency, working on their Sustainable Future mission. This mission focuses on accelerating home heating decarbonisation in the UK, with heat pumps as the primary solution in most cases. Aidan holds a PhD in particle physics from UCL. Since leaving academia, he has developed a strong interest in generative AI, integrating it into many of the projects he has worked on and led. His recent work includes building and evaluating an AI chatbot for heat pump installers and modelling the heat pump suitability of British homes. Aidan contributed to the task of identifying when heat pumps have issues with their weather compensation curves as well as being one of the facilitators for this challenge.

Bivin Pradeep is a PhD candidate at the Centre for Computational Science and Mathematical Modelling at Coventry University. His research focuses on reinforcement learning applications in energy efficiency and robotics. With a background in IoT and sustainability-focused projects, he worked as a research assistant at UAE University, developing proof-of-concept IoT solutions for air quality monitoring, water conservation, and building energy optimisation. His research interests include optimising energy consumption in IoT devices and robotic platforms, particularly in precision agriculture and industrial automation. Bivin contributed to the task by developing a comprehensive, data-driven

framework that integrates predictive modelling, a simulation environment, and a reinforcement learning-based adaptive control strategy for heat pump systems.

Thomas Safar holds an MSc in Social Data Science from the University of Oxford, where he specialised in the application of econometric and machine learning methodologies for causal inference. His contributions to the project range from preprocessing installation and monitoring time series data to applying time series decomposition and causal discovery algorithms. His analysis sheds light on potential causes of underperformance, including the degradation of performance over time and specific installation configurations.

Jonathan Saliba has an MSc in Mechanical Engineering from the Technical University of Delft, the Netherlands. He is a data scientist in industry relating to the domains of transport, logistics and thermal engineering. He contributed to this project through the facilitation of the interpretation of the physical outputs from the Electrification of Heat dataset, working on extracting the isolated compressor power from the time series.

Dequn Teng is a third-year Ph.D. candidate in Engineering and a Cambridge Trust International Scholar at the Center for Technology Management, Institute for Manufacturing, University of Cambridge. His doctoral research examines human–algorithm interactions’ effects on analytical creativity in algorithmic trading strategy formulation. His long-term research identity focuses on emerging algorithmic innovations’ effects on strategic value creation, bridging insights from computer engineering, technology management, and organisational strategy. He contributed to this project by building a cross-sectional regression model that decomposes heat pump performance into technical specifications, building characteristics, and installation quality, demonstrating the interaction effects of the specifications could significantly influence efficiency.

Jing Wei Teoh is an assistant professor at the School of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, Heriot-Watt University Malaysia. His research interests include statistical process control, anomaly detection, and machine learning. He contributed to this project by working on peak detection, clustering of time series, dimensionality reduction via factor analysis, as well as a few unsuccessful attempts, such as regime switching models and process monitoring via control charts.

Maxime Theisen is a PhD student in biophysics and AI at the Department of

Chemistry, University of Cambridge. He has an MSci in Systems Biology and a BA in Physics from the University of Cambridge. He contributed to this project by running the clustering on individual peaks. He isolated peaks with the z-score algorithm, then clustered them with two DTW-based k-means methods and evaluated clusters with silhouette scores. He ran ANOVA and Tukey's HSD tests to evaluate the correlation of COP with individual clusters.

Apostolos Vavouris is a researcher at the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, University of Strathclyde, Scotland, specialising in co-creation of data extraction methods to meet utility, privacy, and trust requirements in energy networks. He contributed to this project by being a facilitator during the DSG event, and through data exploratory analysis (HP distribution, indoor & outdoor temperature) and feature engineering and extraction from the electricity consumption signal (daily and intra-daily) that were used for clustering HPs in Approach 2.

Zhihao Zhang is a PhD student at the School of Energy, Geoscience, Infrastructure and Society, Heriot-Watt University, Scotland, UK. His research focuses on AI-driven and applied data science methods for urban environments, with an emphasis on the building sector. He holds an MSc in Urban Data Science and Analytics from the University of Leeds. He contributed to this project by processing installation data and applying explainable AI techniques to investigate the factors influencing heat pump performance.

10 Principal investigator

Francisco Gómez Medina is a Research Application Manager in Data-Centric Engineering at The Alan Turing Institute. As a RAM, he focuses on translating cutting-edge AI/ML research into applications that help solve the most pressing challenges in industry, government, and academia. He is also a researcher and advisor of CIEMAT, Spain's Centre for Environmental Technology Research, focusing on the deployment of digital twins in solar thermal power plants. Before joining the Turing, he completed his PhD at the Institute for Manufacturing, University of Cambridge. His doctoral research focused on understanding the value of Digital Twins in heavy asset industries, such as aerospace and wind renewables. As part of his research, he has produced several industry reports and research publications which are available upon request. Prior to his PhD, he worked at the Bristol Robotics Laboratory and co-founded two startups in the

gamified advertising and education sectors. He holds a MEng degree in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Bristol.

References

- [1] ABDI, H., AND VALENTIN, D. Multiple correspondence analysis. Encyclopedia of measurement and statistics 2, 4 (2007), 651–657.
- [2] ABDI, H., AND WILLIAMS, L. J. Principal component analysis. Wiley interdisciplinary reviews: computational statistics 2, 4 (2010), 433–459.
- [3] AND, P. S. Modified lilliefors goodness-of-fit test for normality. Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation 51, 3 (2022), 1199–1219.
- [4] BARANDIER, P., AND CARDOSO, A. J. M. A review of fault diagnostics in heat pumps systems. Applied Thermal Engineering 228 (2023), 120454.
- [5] BRAKEL, J. v. Robust peak detection algorithm using z-scores. <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/22583391/peak-signal-detection-in-realtime-timeseries-data/22640362# 22640362>, 2014.
- [6] FLANDRIN, P., RILLING, G., AND GONCALVES, P. Empirical mode decomposition as a filter bank. IEEE signal processing letters 11, 2 (2004), 112–114.
- [7] GOLD, O., AND SHARIR, M. Dynamic time warping: Breaking the quadratic barrier. CoRR abs/1607.05994 (2016).
- [8] JANZING, D., AND SCHÖLKOPF, B. Causal inference using the algorithmic markov condition. IEEE Transactions on Information Theory 56, 10 (2010), 5168–5194.
- [9] LI, P., STUART, E. A., AND ALLISON, D. B. Multiple imputation: A flexible tool for handling missing data. JAMA 314, 18 (2015), 1966–1967.
- [10] MOUGAN, C., PLANT, R., TENG, C., BAZZI, M., EGEA, A. C., CHAN, R. S., JASIN, D. S., STOFFEL, M., WHITAKER, K. J., AND MANSER, J. How to data in datathons. In NeurIPS (2023).
- [11] PAGÈS, J. Analyse factorielle de données mixtes. Revue de Statistique Appliquée 52, 4 (2004), 93–111.

- [12] PROKHORENKOVA, L., GUSEV, G., VOROBEV, A., DOROGUSH, A. V., AND GULIN, A. CatBoost: unbiased boosting with categorical features. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (2018), vol. 31, Curran Associates, Inc.
- [13] SCHULMAN, J., WOLSKI, F., DHARIWAL, P., RADFORD, A., AND KLIMOV, O. Proximal policy optimization algorithms, 2017.
- [14] SPIRITES, P., GLYMOUR, C. N., AND SCHEINES, R.
- [15] TANG, F., AND ISHWARAN, H. Random forest missing data algorithms. Statistical Analysis and Data Mining: An ASA Data Science Journal 10, 6 (2017), 363–377.
- [16] TOWERS, M., KWIATKOWSKI, A., TERRY, J., BALIS, J. U., COLA, G. D., DELEU, T., GOULÃO, M., KALLINTERIS, A., KRIMMEL, M., KG, A., PEREZ-VICENTE, R., PIERRÉ, A., SCHULHOFF, S., TAI, J. J., TAN, H., AND YOUNIS, O. G. Gymnasium: A standard interface for reinforcement learning environments, 2024.
- [17] UHLER, C., RASKUTTI, G., BÜHLMANN, P., AND YU, B. Geometry of the faithfulness assumption in causal inference. The Annals of Statistics 41, 2 (2013), 436–463.
- [18] YU, K., LIU, L., LI, J., AND CHEN, H. Mining markov blankets without causal sufficiency. IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems 29, 12 (2018), 6333–6347.

A Geographical coverage

One might be interested in understanding how the Seasonal Performance Factors (SPF) vary across heat pumps operating at different locations, as well as across low- and high-temperature heat pumps. Figure 31 shows the distribution of these heat pumps together with their SPF values encoded via a colour palette. It may be argued that high-temperature heat pumps generally have higher SPF values (as indicated by lighter colours of the points).

Figure 31: Geographical distribution of the SPF values of low-temperature (left) and high-temperature (right) air source heat pumps

B Winter data availability and COP

COP and other variables in winter Since the seasonality and external temperature have implication for the HPs performance, the instantaneous 24-hr COP and corresponding mean of the external air temperature over the winter of 156 properties can be illustrated in a scatter plot as shown in Figure 32. The figure shows a better picture of the relationship between COP and external air temperature, highlighting the underperformance of HPs occurring on a cold day. A considerably significant number of data points in darker colours (red) indicate that HPs perform poorly as the external air temperature drops. At the same time, HPs showed better performance (blue) as external air temperature rises.

Further exploration, which highlights the variation in HP performance during the day in winter, can be seen in the box plot of the 6-hr interval COP - LT ASHP

COP and External Air Temperature below 10C in Winter

Figure 32: Scatter plot of COP and External air temperature below 10°C in Winter of 156 properties.

of 156 properties, as shown in Figure 33. The figure shows a slight drop in COP during the midnight to morning (0:00-6:00) and evening to midnight (18:00-23:58) at a median of approximately 2.6 and 2.8, respectively. COP during the day is around 3 from morning (6:02-12:00) to evening (12:02-18:00).

It is also worth exploring important monitoring data such as HP Heat Flow Temperature, which indicates HP operating heat flow temperature and the degree to which HPs struggled to keep it during the winter. The heating efficiency of HPs can be illustrated in a scatter plot of the instantaneous 24-hr COP and corresponding mean of the HP Heat Flow Temperature over the winter 156 properties, as shown in Figure 34. The figure shows most of the time HPs performed inefficiently at HP Heat Flow Temperature of around 20-40°C with COP less than 3 (in red), while at some point, HPs also performed efficiently at HP Heat Flow Temperature of around 25-30°C with COP more than 3 (in blue). When comparing to HPs operating during cold day in winter which external air temperature dropped below 10°C, the figure shows HPs operated efficiently at HP Heat Flow Temperature of approximately 28°C as shown in Figure 35, while HPs operated poorly when HP Heat Flow Temperature dropped below 25°C. The

Figure 33: Boxplot of 6-hr interval COP - LT ASHP of 156 properties.

figure also indicates some HPs operating at high HP Heat Flow Temperature around 35°C and 50°C have poor efficiency with considerably low COP, which highlights the underperformed HPs. It is worthwhile to explore these underperformed HPs and indicate the issues.

Figure 34: Scatter plot of COP and HP Flow Temperature in Winter of 156 properties.

COP and HP Flow Temperature when External Air Temperature below 10C in Winter

Figure 35: Scatter plot of COP and HP Flow Temperature when External Temperature below 10°C in Winter of 156 properties.

Figure 36: 2-minute 24-hour winter [22-23] COP of 10 properties.

C One-dimensional peak finding algorithm

Algorithm 1 One-Dimensional Peak Finding Algorithm

Require: Specify array size $n \geq 3$, data array $A[n]$, empty array $B[]$

```
for i in range(1,n,1) do
    if  $A[i-1] \leq A[i]$  AND  $A[i] \geq A[i+1]$  then
        B.append(i)
    end if
end for
Return B
```

D Clusters between COP and different power consumption features extracted

Figure 37: Clusters correlation between COP and the different features.

E Silhouette scores for DTW clustering

Figure 38: Silhouette Scores for DBA and SDTW k-mean for different values of k . SDTW generally performs better than DBA and we achieve the highest silhouette scores for $k = 2$ and $k = 5$

F SHAP value impact on SPFH4 prediction

Figure 39: SHAP Value Impact on SPFH4 Prediction

G Reinforcement learning based adaptive control strategy

In this section, we explore a reinforcement learning based approach to control heat pump systems. Traditionally, thermostats use a fixed rule-based strategy, such as a weather compensation curve to adjust the heating flow temperature. In our proposed approach, we try to leverage the historical monitoring data of heat pumps

to first build a predictive model. After which we create a simulation environment that uses the predictive model to simulate the heat pump dynamics and to train a Reinforcement Learning (RL) agent to learn an adaptive control policy.

G.1 Research questions

G.1.1 Reinforcement Learning based adaptive control strategy

How does an RL-based control strategy compare to traditional rule-based weather compensation in terms of maintaining a target indoor temperature? What is the learning behaviour of the RL agent over time, and how quickly does it converge to an effective control policy?

—Future work needs to be explored— Can the RL-based controller achieve energy savings compared to the conventional approach without compromising comfort? How does the RL-based controller respond to variations in external conditions or system anomalies? To what extent can the RL-based control policy, once trained on a particular installation’s data, be generalised or transferred to other heat pump systems with similar characteristics? The following research questions are looked at in this section

- How does an RL-based control strategy compare to traditional rule-based weather compensation in terms of maintaining a target indoor temperature?
- What is the learning behaviour of the RL agent over time, and how quickly does it converge to an effective control policy?

G.2 Sample selection

To develop the prediction model needed by the RL algorithm to train on, we selected a representative, high-performing heat pump from the dataset. Specifically, EOH0567 was chosen because it demonstrates superior performance within the subset of Low-Temperature Air Source Heat Pumps (ASHP). Key parameters—including internal air temperature, external air temperature, heating flow temperature, and cumulative energy output—were used because they directly affect both the thermal comfort inside the building and the operational efficiency of the heat pump system. The heating flow temperature, which is traditionally adjusted using a rule-based weather compensation curve, along with the derived instantaneous power (computed from cumulative energy data), effectively captures the dynamic response of the system. By leveraging these data

points, we built a robust, data-driven model that simulates system behaviour and serves as the foundation for training an RL-based controller aimed at improving upon conventional, fixed-rule strategies.

G.3 Approach

The aim is to develop an adaptive, data-driven alternative to traditional rule-based weather compensation control methods in heat pump systems. Conventional control strategies rely on predefined weather compensation curves, which adjust heating flow temperature based on external air temperature. However, these fixed-rule approaches may not always optimise energy efficiency or dynamically adapt to variations in real-world conditions. In contrast, our approach leverages reinforcement learning (RL) to develop a control policy that learns directly from system interactions. By integrating a data-driven predictive model with an RL agent, we aim to regulate indoor temperature dynamically, improving both comfort levels and energy efficiency. The proposed framework consists of three key stages:

Predictive Modelling using Linear Regression: A multi-output linear regression model is trained using historical monitoring data from a high-performing low-temperature air source heat pump. The model predicts the next internal air temperature and heating flow temperature based on key system parameters such as internal and external air temperatures, measured heating flow temperature, and instantaneous energy output. By capturing the dynamic behaviour of the heat pump system, this model serves as the core simulation mechanism for evaluating control strategies.

Simulation Environment Development: The simulation environment is developed using the Gymnasium framework [16], integrating the predictive model to approximate system dynamics. The state representation includes current and lagged values of internal and heating flow temperatures, external air temperature, and energy output, ensuring both present conditions and recent history are captured. To establish a stable benchmark for evaluation, fixed values were assigned for certain parameters such as:

- The target indoor temperature was set to 21°C, representing a comfortable heating level.
- A nominal power output of 1.0 kWh was assigned for the action of turning ON the heat pump, while OFF action resulted in 0 kWh consumption.

- The external air temperature was fixed at 10°C to simplify initial training and evaluation.

These choices create a controlled environment where the RL agent’s decisions directly influence system behaviour, allowing us to measure its ability to regulate heating without external disturbances.

Adaptive Control via Reinforcement Learning: The RL agent was trained using the Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) algorithm [13], a widely used method for optimizing control policies. The agent learns by interacting with the environment, receiving rewards based on its ability to maintain indoor temperature near the target. The agent follows a trial-and-error learning process, where it explores different heating strategies and adjusts its actions based on observed outcomes. The reward function is designed to penalise deviations from the target temperature, encouraging the agent to optimise control actions dynamically. In the early training phase the agent explores random actions, often leading to large temperature fluctuations and high penalties. After which the agent experiments with different heating patterns, reducing deviations but still overshooting the target occasionally. Finally, the agent learns to balance heating cycles efficiently, preventing unnecessary energy consumption while maintaining indoor temperature stability.

To summarise, the control decisions are discrete actions (e.g., turning the heat pump on or off), with the agent receiving rewards based on the negative absolute error between the predicted internal temperature and the target. Through training, the agent learns to toggle heating strategically, activating the heat pump in short bursts when needed, rather than keeping it continuously ON or OFF. This adaptive control behaviour contrasts with traditional rule-based heating schedules, which rely solely on external temperature conditions rather than real-time system dynamics.

G.4 Experimental results

The RL agent was trained in a simulated heat pump environment that replicates system behaviour using a predictive model. The environment state vector consists of six key variables: current internal temperature, previous internal temperature, current heating flow temperature, previous heating flow temperature, external air temperature, and instantaneous energy output. The training was conducted over 500,000 time-steps, with each episode running for a maximum of 100 steps

(corresponding to 200 minutes per episode). Actions were discrete, where 1.0 kW was applied when the heat pump was turned on and 0 kW when off. The external air temperature was fixed at 10°C throughout training and evaluation.

G.4.1 Predictive model evaluation

The linear regression model was trained and evaluated using an 80-20 train-test split, where 80% of the available heat pump monitoring data was used for training and 20% for evaluation. The model achieved a Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 0.8199 and a Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.6518

Figure 40: Actual vs Predicted Internal Temperature for Heat pump EOH0567 with 80-20 train-test split

These results indicate that the predictive model is able to approximate system dynamics with reasonable accuracy, though some deviations exist. As seen from Figure 40 the model effectively captures the overall trend of internal temperature changes. In the case of Figure 41, the model tracks the general behaviour of the heating flow temperature. Overall, the linear regression model provides a strong foundation for simulating heat pump behaviour within the RL environment.

G.4.2 RL agent performance

The trained Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) agent was evaluated over 50 test episodes to assess its ability to maintain the target indoor temperature of 21°C. The

Figure 41: Actual vs Predicted Heat pump Flow Temperature for EOH0567 with 80-20 train-test split

RL agent interacts with the simulation environment by selecting actions at each step (either turning the heat pump ON or OFF), and in response, the environment updates the system state using the learned predictive model. The agent receives a reward based on how close the indoor temperature remains to the target.

During training, the RL agent started with no prior knowledge about how to control the heat pump. Initially, it explored random actions, leading to large fluctuations in indoor temperature and unstable rewards. However, over time, the agent learned to associate actions with temperature regulation outcomes, progressively improving its control strategy. After sufficient experience, the agent learned to balance heating cycles, efficiently toggling between ON and OFF states to maintain indoor temperature within an acceptable range, thereby achieving higher rewards (lower deviation from 21°C).

As can be seen from Figure 42, the final 50 evaluation episodes demonstrate that the RL agent was able to maintain the indoor temperature reasonably close to the target of 21°C. The total episode rewards are stable across the different episodes, which indicates that the strategy learned by the agent is consistent across different scenarios.

Figure 42: Episode evaluation of reward vs final indoor temperature reached by the trained RL-agent

G.5 Implications and future considerations

However, despite successful temperature regulation, certain limitations were observed, such as the agent settling slightly above the target temperature, which suggests fine-tuning the reward function to penalise overheating slightly more could improve stability. Also, since the external air temperature and the heat pump output were fixed, the agent was not able to experience variable conditions, which would be essential for real-world deployments. The current approach only allows on/off switching, whereas controlling the flow temperature directly could offer finer adjustments and better efficiency. These findings suggest that while RL-based control offers adaptive decision-making, further refinements are needed to enhance robustness and efficiency.

H EMD applied to various time series

Figure 43: The EMD fitted to various different time series, with different number of IMFs extracted

I Flow temperature vs external temperature plot for property ID 3056

Figure 44: This scatter plot displays flow temperature versus external temperature for a Vaillant heat pump (property ID 3056) during 12-01-23 to 12-02-23. Colors differentiate operating modes: orange for active DHW cycles, green for the two minutes following DHW, blue when non-operational, and purple for space heating operation.

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**